

Welcome to the EXA4MIND Newsletter

Who are we? We are a Horizon Europe project that builds an extreme data platform that brings together large scale data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures by implementing novel automated data management and effective data staging.

Events

EXA4MIND makes its mark at SCA/HPCAsia 2026

At the end of January, Osaka (Japan) became the **meeting point for the global high-performance computing community** as it hosted [SCA/HPCAsia 2026](#), a major HPC event in the Asia-Pacific region. The conference brought together

two important events – SupercomputingAsia (SCA) and HPCAsia – creating a forum for researchers, industry experts, and technology providers.

The **EXA4MIND partners** used this opportunity to present the project and its outcomes. Mohamad Hayek from the [Leibniz Supercomputing Centre](#) introduced the poster “Tapping Data Spaces in HPC: Enabling, Exploring and Benchmarking Database & Object Store Usage.” The poster “Easy Molecular Dynamics on HPC with EXA4MIND” was presented by David Číž from [IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center](#). The project coordinator Jan Martinovič explained the “EXA4MIND AI Inference Service Solution” and Pinar Karagoz from [Middle East Technical University](#) presented the poster “How to Make Data Pipeline Scalable: A Case Study for Healthcare Data Analytics”.

Discover more

PLENARY MEETING

FEBRUARY 2026
25 - 27
OSTRAVA

 Funded by the European Union

EXA4MIND hosts its last plenary meeting in Ostrava

From 25 to 27 February 2026, the EXA4MIND consortium met at the [VSB – Technical University of Ostrava](#) in the Czech Republic, for the **project’s final face-to-face plenary meeting**. Hosted by [IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center](#), the meeting provided an important opportunity for the consortium to review all the milestones and deliverables they will work on over the next two months before the project officially concludes at the end of April.

In addition to the discussions, the EXA4MIND consortium had the **privilege of visiting the IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center facilities**,

where the consortium saw first-hand the [Barbora](#) and [Karolina](#) supercomputers and the [VLQ quantum computer](#), developed by the [LUMI-Q consortium](#).

[Discover more](#)

EXAKI trainings

Smart farms and extreme datasets

EXA4MIND

TRAINING PROVIDED BY EXA4MIND

SMART FARMS AND EXTREME DATASETS

EVGENY BOGDANOV

TERRAVIEW

Funded by the European Union

This first webinar by [Terraview](#) demonstrates how Earth observation and drone technologies power smart farms in agriculture. It details the agritech solutions such as crop-agnostic Aquaview tool for soil moisture monitoring and Gamaya Viewer's suite of solutions for viticulture. Besides, it introduces an Extreme Datasets problem and the **potential of the EXA4MIND platform** to address this issue.

[Download the full presentation here](#)

How Airflow powers Aquaview

This second webinar by Terraview showcases how Airflow is used to deliver large-scale soil moisture **content analysis of agricultural fields** with Aquaview.

[Download the full presentation here](#)

Use of AI for big data processing and understanding for validation of ADAS

In this EXA4MIND training, David Hurych from [Valeo](#) presents the latest methods and AI models for processing image, LiDAR, and text data used in the validation of ADAS before they are deployed on the road in real traffic. The

presentation also describes unsupervised machine learning **methods developed within the platform for extreme data** of the **EXA4MIND** project for the transfer, storage, and analysis of extremely large-scale data using supercomputers and cloud technologies.

[Download the full presentation here](#)

How big data processing helps with molecular dynamics data processing

EXA4MIND

TRAINING PROVIDED BY EXA4MIND

HOW BIG DATA PROCESSING HELPS WITH MOLECULAR DYNAMICS DATA PROCESSING

DAVID ČÍŽ

IT4INNOVATIONS

Funded by the European Union

Molecular dynamics simulations produce enormous volumes of valuable data, but turning them into useful insight is challenging. In this training, David Číž from [IT4Innovations](#) presents **how the EXA4MIND extreme data platform automates simulation data processing** using extracting key metadata and preparing results for efficient analysis. The end-to-end workflow demonstrates how modern data orchestration accelerates research in computational chemistry and materials science.

[Download the full presentation here](#)

Supercomputing with versatile data backends, part I

EXA4MIND enables researchers, industry and SMEs to run Extreme Data analytics workflows leveraging top-tier supercomputing facilities across Europe. To this end, it provides an open platform of flexibly-deployable modules & submodules. Efficient analytics heavily depend on optimum object-store and database management systems, and on proper analytics workflows, for which **EXA4MIND provides its Advanced Query & Indexing System (AQIS)** with inferencing and cross-system-query capabilities.

In this webinar, the [Leibniz Supercomputing Centre](#) (BADW-LRZ) makes you familiar with databases and S3-compatible object stores, and give you a feeling on **how EXA4MIND helps** you to deploy them in a data centre or on your standalone machine. The webinar will be followed up by a second part, introducing you to actual data analytics with AQIS, leveraging Airflow and Dask.

Download the full
presentation here

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